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The Influence Of Alcohol Among Secondary School Students In Etche Local Government Area Of Rivers State: With Implication For Counselling

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of alcohol among secondary school students in Etche local government area of rivers state: with implication for counseling. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of all the secondary school students in the area. The sample of the study composed 200 students drawn through stratified sampling technique. Taro Yamane was used in selecting the sample size. The instrument for data collection was a self-designed questionnaire titled: 'the influence of alcohol among secondary school students in Etche local government area of rivers state: with implications for counseling Questionnaire.' The instrument was validated by two expertises from the department of Educational Psychology, Guidance and Counselling. Test-retest method was used in determining the reliability of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while independent t-test was used in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The result showed the influence of alcohol among secondary school students based on gender, parental socio-economic status, class level and school type in Etche local government area of rivers state. Based on the findings, recommendations such as teachers and parents should help their children to build self-esteem which will help them resist the urge to bend to peer pressure.

Keywords: alcohol, counselling, students, self-esteem

INTRODUCTION

Several studies have reported that alcohol use during adolescence affects educational attainment by decreasing the number of years of schooling and the like hood of completing school (Chatterji & De Simone, 2005; Cook & Moore, 1993; Gil-Lacruz & Molina, 2017; Koch & McGear, 2005; McCluskey, Krohn, Zizotte, & Rodriquez, 2002; NIDA, 1998, Renna, 2007; yamada, Kendrix, & Yamada 1996) other research using alternative estimation techniques suggest that the effects of teens drinking on years of education and schooling completion are very small and/or non-significant (Chatterji, 2006; Dee & Evans, 2003; Koch & Ribar, 2001).

Despite a growing literature in this area, no study has convincingly answered the question of whether alcohol consumption inhibits high school students' learning. Alcohol consumption could be an important determinant of how much a high school student learns without having a strong impact on his or her decision to stay in school or attend college. This question is fundamental and timely, given recent research showing that underage drinkers are susceptible to the immediate consequences of alcohol use, including blackouts, hangovers, and alcohol poisoning, and are at elevated risk of neurodegeneration

(particularly in regions of the brain responsible for learning and memory), impairments in functional brain activity, and neurocognitive defects (Zeiglers et al., 2004).

A common and comprehensive measure of secondary school students' learning is Grade Point Average (GPA). GPA is an important outcome because it is a key determinant of college admissions decisions and of job quality for those who do not attend college. Only a few studies have explored the association between alcohol use and GPA. Wolaver (2002) and Williams, Powell, and Wechsler (2003) have studied this association among college students, while DeSimone and Wolaver (2005) have investigated the effects of underage drinking on GPA during high school.

Understanding the relationship between teenage drinking and high school grades is pertinent given the high prevalence of alcohol use among this age cohort and recent research on adolescent brain development suggesting that early heavy alcohol use may have negative effects on the physical development of brain structure (Brown, Taper, Granholm, & Delis, 2002; Taper & Brown, 1999).

In this study, the effects of drinking in high school on the quality of learning will be estimated. The focus being on the effect of drinking on academic achievement during secondary school. To date and to the best of my knowledge, only one other study in the literature has analyzed the consequences of underage drinking on secondary school scores. Fixed-effects techniques are superior to instrumental variables (IV) estimation when the strength and reliability of the instruments are suspect (French & Popovici, 2009). In addition to analyzing mediators related to exposure to education, we investigate the effect of drinking on students' ability to focus on and adhere to academic objectives.

Alcoholism has become a common practice especially among students in Rivers State. Most of the students find it necessary to use alcoholic beverages in order to feel comfortable or if their lives are lacking meaning they resort to taking alcoholic drinks as a reliever to them.

An addicted person could be psychologically dependent on alcohol; this means that the person thinks he or she must take alcoholic drinks at all times. His body may actually need it or not need it at all. But the point is that, he goes on craving for it because he thinks he needs it. This craving can be so strong that he finds it difficult to give it up.

An addicted person could also be physically dependent on alcohol. This means that the person's body actually needs the alcohol.

Statement of the problem

There is a general observation that the students in Port Harcourt have a serious problem of alcoholism which affects them psychologically, physically and also academically. Alcoholism is a habit that is difficult to quit.

Most of the students have become psychologically and socially dependent on alcohol. This tends to manifest in their day to day activities where by most of them find it hard to work without taking some alcoholic beverages. Alcohol consumption is a serious public health challenge worldwide, including in Nigeria. Although the level of alcohol consumption differs widely around the world, the burden of disease and death remains significant in most regions, with Europe and America having the highest alcohol attributable fractions at 6.5% and 5.6%, respectively. Recent evidence also indicates that alcohol consumption is now the world's third largest risk factor for disease and disability; almost 4% of all deaths globally are attributed to alcohol. However, alcohol is the most commonly used psychoactive drug in both young people and adults in Nigeria. Some of the factors contributing to alcohol consumption among Nigerians include the absence of alcohol policies, easy access to alcohol drinks, and lack of implementation of a minimum drinking age by both the government and the brewers.

According to Bola and Adebisi, it is not rare for Nigerian secondary school students to consume alcoholic drink; this consumption could be due to their curiosity as adolescents, an irresistible urge, emotional disturbances such as anxiety, the subculture, and the influence of advertisements. Several previous studies have shown the prevalence of alcohol consumption among the Nigerian population, but they did not explore adolescent students understanding of its negative health effects. For instance, Lasebikan and Ola found that the prevalence of life time alcohol use was 57.9% and that of current alcohol use was 27.3% among a sample of Nigerian semirural community dwellers. Through in-person interviews with Nigerian

adults, previous research revealed that the life time prevalence of alcohol consumption was 56%. A recent study showed that the prevalence of current alcohol consumption among a sample of Nigerian secondary school students was 30.6% and that 38.1% of current drinkers had also been drunk in the past 30 days, with 17.2% being drunk very frequently. Although 18 years of age is the legal limit for alcohol consumption per policy in many parts of the world, socio-cultural influences seem to hinder strict adherence to this public health policy in Nigerian society (Major Foundation for Medical Education and Research, 2021).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the influence of alcohol among secondary school students in Etche local government area of rivers state.

The Specific Objectives of this study are:

1. To identify if poverty is a cause of alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.
2. To examine the influence of peer group on alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.
3. To determine the effects of alcoholism on the students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Research Questions

These research questions guided this study:

1. Is poverty a cause of alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State?
2. Does peer group influence alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State?
3. What are the effects of alcohol on the students in Etche local government area of Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 levels of significance guided this study

Null hypotheses (Ho)

1. There is no relationship between socio-economic status of students and alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.
2. There is no relationship between peer group and alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.
3. There is no relationship between secondary school students performance and alcohol in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Alternate hypotheses (H1)

1. There is a relationship between socio-economic status of students and alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.
2. There is a relationship between peer group and alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.
3. There is a relationship between secondary school students performance and alcoholism in etch local government area of Rivers State.

Operational Definition of Terms

Student: is a person of moderate and productive age.

Alcoholism: is a condition caused by uncontrollable intake of alcoholic beverages.

Alcoholic beverages/drinking: are drinks that contain alcohol such as lever, wine, and spirit that can make people drunk.

Alcoholics: are those excessive drinkers whose dependence on alcoholic drinks has drink too much alcoholic beverages and cannot easily stop drinking because it has become all illness to him/her.

Delinquency: Minor crime especially committed by a youth.

METHODS

Research methodology presented in this study is as follow: Research design, population of the study, sampling technique, sample, instrument for data collection, validation of the instrument, reliability of the instrument, administration of the instrument, and method of data analysis.

Design

The study will adopt the correlational research designs which are useful in determining whether two or more variables are related. These were adopted to investigate the influence of poverty, peer group on alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The presentation of data was based on the research questions and hypotheses earlier stated in the study.

Research Question One

Is poverty a cause of alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State?

Table 1: Response of Students on influence of socio-economic status on alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche Local Government Area.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Students who said poverty is the cause of alcoholism	5	0.02	0.36	-0.953
Students who said poverty is not the cause of alcoholism	186	0.973	23.38	

Result in Table1. Shows that the mean response of students who said poverty is the cause of alcoholism is 0.02 with a standard deviation of 0.36 on the other hand, the mean response of students who said poverty is not cause of alcoholism is 0.973 with a standard deviation of 13.38. The mean difference between the response of students who said poverty is the cause of alcoholism and students who said poverty is not the cause of alcoholism is -0.953. The result of this research question is that poverty is not the cause of alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Hypotheses One

There is no relationship between socio-economic status of students and alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area.

Table 2: Independent sample t-test of the mean response of students on influence of socio-economic status on alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area.

Variable	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal	P-value	Remark
Students who said poverty is the cause of alcoholism.	5	0.02	0.36	189	202.7	1.960	Not sign.
Students who said poverty is not the cause of alcoholism	186	0.973	13.38				H_0 is not rejected

Alpha level = 0.05

Result in Table 2. Indicates that the calculated t-value is 202.7 while the p-value is 1.960 and the chosen alpha level is 0.05. This shows that the p-value is greater than the significant level ($p > 0.5$). Therefore the null hypothesis is not rejected. This revealed that there is no relationship between socio-economic status of students and alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area.

Research Question Two: *Does peer group influence alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State?*

Table3. Response of students as regards influence of peer group on alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government of Rivers State.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Students who said peer group influences alcoholism	76	0.40	5.47	
Students who said peer group does not influence alcoholism	115	0.06	8.28	-0.2

Result in Table 3 reveals that the response of students who said peer group influences alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State is 0.40 with a standard deviation of 5.47 on the other hand, the mean response of students who said peer group does not influence alcoholism is 0.60 with standard deviation of 8.28. However, the mean difference between the response of students who said peer group does not influence alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government of River state is -0.2. The result of this research question is that peer pressure does not influence alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government of Rivers State.

Hypothesis two

There is no relationship between peer group and among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Table 4: Independent sample t-test of the mean response of students as regards influence of peer group on alcoholism among Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Variable	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal	P-value	Remark
Students who said that peer group influences alcoholism	76	0.40	5.47				Signit
Students who said that peer group does not influence alcoholism	115	0.60	8.28	189	-4	1.960	H ₀ is not rejected

Alpha level = 0.05

Result in Table 4. Indicates that the calculated t-value is -4 while the p-value is 1.960 and the chosen alpha level is 0.05. This result reveals that the p-value is more than significance level ($p > 0.5$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This revealed that there is no relationship between peer group and alcoholism among secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Research Question Three

What are the effects of alcoholism on the students in Etche local government area of Rivers State?

Table 5: Response of students on the effects of alcoholism among Secondary School Students in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State.

Variable	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Students who said that alcoholism negatively affects students.	81	0.42	5.83	
Students who said that alcoholism does not affect students negatively	110	0.58	7.92	-0.16

Result in Table 5. Shows that the mean response of students who said that alcoholism affects secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State negatively is 0.42 with a standard deviation of 5.83 on the other hand, the mean performance of students who said that alcoholism does not affect secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State is negatively 0.58 with a standard deviation of 7.92. However, the mean difference of students who said that alcoholism affects secondary school students negatively and those that said that alcoholism does not affect secondary school students negatively in Etche local government area of Rivers State is -0.16. The result of this research

question is that alcoholism does not affect secondary school students in Etche local government area of Rivers State negatively.

Hypothesis Three

There is no relationship between secondary school student performance and alcoholism in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Table 6: Independent sample t-test of the mean response students on effects of alcoholism among secondary students in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Variable	N	Mean	Std	Df	t-cal	p-value	Remark
Students who said that alcoholism affects students negatively	81	0.42	5.83	189	-3.14	1.960	Signit
Students who said that alcoholism does not affect students negatively	110	0.58	7.92				H ₀ is rejected

Alpha level = 0.05

Result in Table 6. Indicates that the calculated t-value is -3.14 while the p-value is 1.960 and the chosen alpha level is 0.05. This shows that the p-value is more than the significance level ($p > 0.5$). Therefore, the null hypothesis is not rejected. This revealed that there is no relationship between alcoholism and secondary school students' performance in Etche local government area of Rivers State.

Implications for Counseling

The results of the research have serious implications for Guidance and Counseling. This result has the implication for counseling services to be provided at all levels of the formal education programme. This will enable learners at that level of education to seek assistance that will enable them realize their potentials and avoid alcoholism.

Another implication of this research is the need to make counseling service functional at all levels of formal education. It is not enough to establish counseling service in the secondary schools but to make it functional by providing all needed facilities and equipment that will enhance the capacity of the counselors in discharging their functions effectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the research, the researcher recommends as follows:

- i. In order to root out alcoholism among secondary school students, there is need for a favorable school environment which encourages vibrant to curricula activities such as sport, music, drama, clubs and societies.
- ii. Parents and guardians should desist from giving students a lot of pocket money which economically empowers them to acquire alcoholic drinks. Parents should also try and shield students from the effects of parental conflicts and family dysfunctions by ensuring those students' physical, emotional and social needs are met.
- iii. The government should regulate the sale of alcohol through licensing, packaging, pricing, restricting the age of consumers and regulating opening hours for the selling points. This will ensure that the selling points are located away from school premises, small portable packages are abolished, prices are non affordable to students, consumers below the age of majority are not accessible to alcohol and selling points are only operational during the night.
- iv. Religious institutions should Endeavour to mould students' spiritual and moral values. This may help schools to resist the urge to indulge.

CONCLUSION

The present study suggests that male secondary school students moderately consume beer and local cocktails, whereas their female counterparts are slight consumers of these 2 alcoholic drinks. Finally, male and female secondary school students significantly differed in their awareness of some of the

negative effects of alcohol consumption on health. Overall, secondary school students are not very aware of some of the negative effects of alcohol on human health. Schools should organize seminars for students to provide education on the health-related issues surrounding alcohol consumption.

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